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2 Delivery: Design, Characterization, and In Vitro Targeting Evaluation
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14 Surface-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) Nanogel Carriers for Oral Vaccine Delivery: Design,
15 Characterization, and In Vitro Targeting Evaluation

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31

32 **Abstract**

33 Oral drug delivery is a route of choice for vaccine administration because of its non-
34 invasive nature and thus efforts have focused on efficient delivery of vaccine antigens to
35 mucosal sites. An effective oral vaccine delivery system must protect the antigen from
36 degradation upon mucosal delivery, penetrate mucosal barriers and control the release
37 of the antigen and costimulatory and immunomodulatory agents to specific immune
38 cells (i.e., APCs). In this paper, mannan-modified pH-responsive P(HEMA-co-MAA)
39 nanogels were synthesized and assessed as carriers for oral vaccination. The nanogels
40 showed pH sensitive properties, entrapping and protecting the loaded cargo at low pH
41 values, and triggered protein release after pH switching to intestinal pH values. Surface
42 decoration with mannan as carbohydrate moieties resulted in enhanced internalization
43 by macrophages as well as increasing the expression of relevant costimulatory
44 molecules. These findings indicate that mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
45 are a promising approach to a more efficacious oral vaccination regimen.

46 **Keywords**

47 Oral vaccine delivery, pH-responsive, nanogels, mannan, targeting, protein delivery

48 **Introduction**

49 Up to date, most licensed vaccines are administered parenterally and result in robust systemic
50 immune response but no mucosal immunity¹. In fact, mucosal delivery is the only vaccination
51 route that induces both mucosal and systemic immune responses² as well as immunization at
52 distant mucosal sites³. Oral drug delivery is a route of choice for vaccine administration because
53 of its non-invasive nature, which improves patient compliance, facilitate administration and
54 distribution, and reduces cost, in comparison to traditional administration methods (i.e.,
55 subcutaneous or intramuscular injections)². However, the low mucosal permeability and lack of

56 stability of most protein-based antigens in the gastrointestinal environment (i.e., gastric acidity
57 and proteolytic enzymes) result in low bioavailability and lack of control on absorbed dose,
58 which makes necessary the use of adjuvants⁴ and slows down products development^{2, 5}. Efforts
59 have focused on efficient delivery of vaccine antigens to mucosal sites, and one of the most
60 promising strategies relies on the use of polymer nanoparticles².

61 Several aspects must be considered in the rational design of oral-delivered nanovaccines. A
62 primary goal is to protect the antigen from degradation upon mucosal delivery and provide
63 controlled release at the targeted site (i.e., antigen-sampling M cells of immune-cell rich Peyer's
64 patches in the small intestine for oral delivery)⁶⁻⁸; the amount of bioactive antigen administrated
65 can determine the Th1/Th2 bias in the immune response⁹ and, according to some authors, induce
66 a specific oral tolerance mechanism upon repeated administration^{7, 10}. Antigen should then be
67 transported to organized mucosal-associated lymphoid tissues (MALT) and presented to antigen-
68 presenting cells (APCs) such as macrophages and dendritic cells (DCs). APCs must be
69 adequately activated in order to generate protective mucosal immune responses⁵. Generating
70 robust protection via cellular (T cell) or humoral (B cell) immune responses highly depends on
71 the mechanisms by which antigen-containing nanoparticles are internalized⁸. In addition to
72 nanoparticle size^{4, 5}, nanoparticle composition (i.e., surface chemistry and polymer architecture)
73 plays a critical role in cell uptake and are of utmost importance in immune activation and
74 modulation¹. Nanoparticle carriers can be designed to emulate pathogen associated molecular
75 patterns (PAMPs), mimicking the entry of pathogens³ and targeting important pathogen
76 recognition receptors (PRRs) on APCs¹¹.

77 In this study, we design novel mannan (MN)-surface conjugated pH-responsive nanogels for
78 targeting C-type lectin receptors (CLRs), which are PRRs with highly conserved carbohydrate-
79 recognition domains and that are highly expressed in cells of the mucosal immune system^{12, 13}, as
80 a strategy to enhance and shape the immune response. Ligand recognition by CLRs leads to

81 pathogen internalization via receptor mediated endocytosis and subsequent degradation and
82 presentation of the pathogen as antigen to T cells by major histocompatibility complex class I or
83 II (MHC I or MHC II), or both, promoting one or both humoral/cellular responses¹⁴. Thus,
84 surface conjugation of CLR ligands (i.e., mannan) in combination with polymer-based
85 strategies has proved to be a powerful approach for the rational design of targeted nanovaccines
86 to induce robust immune responses¹⁵.

87 Our research team has largely worked on protein oral delivery by means of pH-responsive
88 hydrogels¹⁶. Extensive studies on methacrylic acid (MAA)-based hydrogel compositions such as
89 poly(methacrylic acid –grafted-ethylene glycol (P(MAA-g-PEG)))¹⁷ and poly(methacrylic acid-
90 co-*N*-vinyl pyrrolidone) (P(MAA-co-NVP))¹⁸ as delivery systems for protein therapeutics such
91 as insulin¹⁹, calcitonin²⁰ and interferon beta²¹ have been successfully carried out within our
92 group. Furthermore, the tunable physicochemical characteristics of these polymer networks
93 allow for modulation of biological activity through attachment of targeting ligands and
94 mucoadhesion enhancers^{22, 23}. Herein, we describe the synthesis of nanogels of poly(2-
95 hydroxiethyl methacrylate-co-methacrylic acid), P(HEMA-co-MAA) and their *in vitro*
96 evaluation as an oral vaccine delivery platform. The surface of these carriers is optimized by the
97 covalent linkage of mannan to mimic carbohydrate moieties found on the surface of pathogens²⁴,
98 providing “pathogen-like” properties to enhance M cell uptake³ and specifically target CLRs on
99 APCs¹⁵, with the additional benefit of potential complement activation²⁵. Results demonstrated
100 the efficacy of the proposed surface-modified pH-responsive nanogels to efficiently release a
101 model antigen in conditions similar to those at the small intestine (i.e., neutral pH) and to be
102 uptaken by and activate APCs (i.e., macrophages).

103 **Materials and methods**

104 **Chemicals**

105 HEMA, MAA, ethylene glycol dimethacrylate (EGDMA), potassium persulphate (KPS),
106 poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) MW 31,000 – 50,000 hydrolyzed 98-99%, ovalbumin from chicken
107 egg (OVA), Mannan from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)
108 carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), MES sodium salt, Dulbecco's
109 Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) – high glucose without L-glutamine, phenol red free DMEM,
110 penicillin, streptomycin, sterile 1X phosphate buffer saline (PBS), Hank's buffered salt solution
111 without (HBSS) calcium and magnesium, chloroacetic acid 99% A.C.S. grade and Alexa
112 Fluor®594 wheat germ-agglutinin (WGA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO).
113 Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), hydrochloric acid (HCl), 100% ethanol, potassium chloride (KCl),
114 glacial acetic acid, nitric acid, acetone, basic alumina, sulfo-*N*-hydroxysuccinimide (sulfo-NHS),
115 ethylenediamine dihydrochloride and paraformaldehyde were obtained from Thermo Fisher
116 Scientific Inc. (Fairlawn, NJ). CellTiter 96® Aqueous Non-Radioactive Cell Proliferation Assay
117 (MTS) was purchased from VWR International (Radnor, PA), and Pro-Long with DAPI was
118 acquired from Molecular Probes Invitrogen (Grand Island, NY).

119 **Methods**

120 **Synthesis of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels**

121 Hydrogels were prepared by thermal-initiated surfactant-free emulsion polymerization as
122 described elsewhere²⁶ with some modification. Prior to use, MAA was vacuum distilled²³ to
123 remove the inhibitor (hydroquinone). HEMA and EGDMA were passed through a basic alumina-
124 column for the same purpose, and stored at 4 °C until use. For the preparation of particles, the
125 stabilizer, poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) was dissolved in 50 mL of ultrapure water (MilliQ Plus,
126 Millipore) for the preparation of the continuous phase, at a concentration of 1, 1.5 or 3% (w/v).
127 In the interim, monomers were mixed at a molar feed ratio of 3:1, 1:1 and 1:3 of HEMA:MAA
128 and at 1 wt % to the continuous phase, to be assayed at each of the PVA concentrations prepared,
129 yielding a total of nine different formulations. The cross-linker, EGDMA was added to the

130 monomers at 1.0 mol% of total monomers. Then, the monomers and cross-linker solution was
131 added to the continuous phase and mixed in an ultrasonic bath (VWR® Symphony Ultrasonic,
132 VWR International) for an hour. Prior to polymerization, potassium persulphate (KPS, initiator)
133 was added in the amount of 0.05 wt % of total monomers, and the mixture was purged with
134 nitrogen for 20 min to remove oxygen. Polymerization was carried out under nitrogen
135 atmosphere and constant magnetic stirring at a temperature of 70 °C for 24 h. After
136 polymerization was completed, particles were purified by washing with methanol and 0.5 N
137 NaOH several times to remove the unreacted monomers. For this purpose, the particles were
138 precipitated and collected by centrifugation (Centra-CL3R with ThermoIEC Rotor, Thermo
139 Electron Corporation) at 25 °C, 3150 rcf for 1 h. The resulting pellets were re-suspended in a 1:1
140 mixture of ethanol and 0.5 N NaOH and the process was repeated four more times. Following,
141 the nanogels were re-suspended in DI water and dialyzed in 100 kDa MWCO Biotech RC
142 dialysis tubing (Spectra/Por®, Rancho Dominguez, CA) and freeze-dried (FreeZone Cascade
143 Benchtop Freeze Drying System, LabConco).

144 **Nanogels characterization**

145 The pH-responsive swelling behavior of the hydrogel nanoparticles was characterized by
146 measuring the z-average diameters and zeta potential using a Malvern ZetaSizer nano ZS
147 (Malvern Instruments Corp., Malvern, UK) equipped with a 633 nm laser source and MPT-2
148 Autotitrator. For this purpose, 2 mg of freeze-dried particles were suspended in 10 mL of 5 mM
149 KCl and filtered through 1.2 µm pore size syringe filters (Whatman Int. Ltd., VWR
150 International) to eliminate larger aggregates. In the measuring process, the autotitrator increased
151 the pH to 11 and then stepwise decreased the pH while measuring the z-average diameter and
152 zeta potential for each pH value. To evaluate particle morphology, nanogels were imaged using a
153 Hitachi S-5500 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (30kV). For this purpose, ~3 mg of
154 nanoparticles were spread on carbon tab previously stuck to aluminium stubs and dried

155 overnight. Samples were sputter coated with a 10 nm gold layer using a Pelco Model 3 sputter
156 coater (Pelco International, Redding, CA).

157 **Surface modification of nanogels**

158 *Synthesis of Carboxymethyl Mannan (CMM)*

159 Carboxymethyl mannan (CMM) was prepared through base-catalyzed methylation^{27, 28}. Briefly,
160 100 mg of Mannan from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were dissolved in 1 mL of DI water and 1
161 mL of 1M NaOH were added dropwise with constant stirring while the solution was kept in an
162 ice bath. After 30 min, 1 mL of a 20% w/v chloroacetic acid solution were subsequently added
163 dropwise and then the mixture was allowed to react at 60 °C for 6 h with constant stirring.
164 Finally, the mixture was cooled down to RT and neutralized with 1M HCl. CMM was collected
165 by precipitation in cold absolute ethanol, dialyzed overnight in DI water and freeze-dried.

166 *Mannan attachment to nanogels*

167 Mannan was conjugated to the surface of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels by an amine-carboxylic
168 acid coupling reaction^{15, 29, 30}. In a previous step, ethylenediamine moieties were attached to the
169 carboxylated mannan (AECM-MN) by incubating a solution of 50 mg of CMM in 1 mL of 0.1
170 M MES at pH 7.4 with 5 mg of 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide hydrochloride
171 (EDC) and 5 mg of sulfo-*N*-hydroxysuccinimide (Sulfo-NHS) to activate the CMM's carboxylic
172 acid groups, and 160 mg of ethylenediamine dihydrochloride. The reaction mixture was
173 incubated at RT for 12 h with constant agitation. After the incubation period, the AECM-MN
174 was purified overnight by dialysis against DI water and freeze-dried. Conjugation of AECM-MN
175 to the surface of nanogels was then performed by suspending the nanogels (2% w/v) in 0.1M
176 MES buffer following by the addition of 5 mg of Sulfo-NHS and 5 mg of EDC; mixture was
177 allowed to react for 30 min at RT with constant end-to-end rotation. After the incubation period
178 was completed, particles were centrifuged 3x at 8,000 rpm for 5 min at 25 °C (Eppendorf

179 MiniSpin Plus, Eppendorf) and the supernatant was removed, to eliminate remaining from
180 reagents. A new incubation was carried out by re-suspending the particles in 500 μ L of 0.1 MES
181 with 0.1 mg of AECM-MN and incubating for 12 h at RT with constant rotation. Then, the
182 particles were centrifuged 3x at 8,000 rpm for 5 min at 25 $^{\circ}$ C, the supernatant removed, and the
183 pellet resuspended once in ethanol and 2x in DI water. Finally, the particles were dried under
184 vacuum for 2 h.

185 **Characterization of Mannan-modified nanogels**

186 The amount of mannan associated to the P(MAA-co-HEMA) nanogels was estimated by
187 differences between the initial amount added and the amount quantified in the supernatants
188 collected during the purification process. The amount of mannan in the initial solution and
189 supernatants samples was estimated by a colorimetric phenol-sulfuric acid assay using a mannan
190 standard curve as a reference. Additionally, an *in vitro* agglutination assay was performed to
191 verify the conjugation of mannan to nanogels and to assess the availability of mannose ligand
192 after conjugation. Briefly, mannan-modified nanogels were dispersed in water (1% w/v) and
193 incubated with concanavalin A (Con-A). Time-dependent increase in turbidity at 550 nm was
194 monitored spectrophotometrically for 3 h³¹. Unmodified nanogels were also assayed with Con-A
195 as control.

196 **Ovalbumin (OVA) loading**

197 OVA loading was done by equilibrium partitioning. Initially, nanogels were incubated overnight
198 in 5 mL of 10 mM phosphate buffer solution (PBS, pH 7.4) with constant end-to-end rotation to
199 assure wetting and swelling of the nanogels. A solution of OVA was prepared at a concentration
200 of 2 mg/mL in PBS, pH 7.4. Before the addition of OVA to the particles, nanogels were allowed
201 to set down for 2 min and a 200- μ L sample of supernatant was taken and filtered using 0.22 μ m
202 PVDF filters (Millipore, Bedford, MA) and then replaced with equal amounts of 10 mM PBS,

203 pH 7.4. Then, 5 mL of OVA solution were added to particles suspension and incubated at room
204 temperature (RT) with constant end-to-end rotation. Supernatant samples were taken at fixed
205 time points; 1, 2, 4, 6 and 24 h. After 24 h of incubation, particles were collapsed using 0.1 N
206 HCl until reaching pH 3.5. The supernatant was removed and its pH adjusted to 7.4 with 0.1 N
207 NaOH, and stored at 4 °C until assayed. The particles were re-suspended with 5 mL of 10 mM
208 PBS at pH 3.5 and vortexed, following by centrifugation at 300 rcf and 25°C for 5 min. The
209 resulting supernatant was again taken and its pH adjusted to 7.4 with 0.1 N NaOH, and stored at
210 4°C until assayed. Finally, the particles pellet was re-suspended in 5 mL of 10 mM PBS at pH
211 3.5 and freeze-dried. Determination of OVA concentration in the supernatant was carried out
212 with a Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Scientific, Sugar Land, TX).

213 Loading efficiency was defined as follows²³ :

$$214 \quad \text{Loading Efficiency} = \frac{C_0 - C_f}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

215 Where C_0 is the initial OVA concentration and C_f is the final OVA concentration remaining in
216 solution.

217 **OVA release**

218 Release studies aimed to simulate the pH changes the P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels would
219 experience *in vivo* when passing through the stomach and into the small intestine (*i.e.*, from an
220 acidic pH to a neutral pH)²³. For this experiment, 5 mg of OVA-loaded nanogels were
221 suspended in low-adhesion microcentrifuge tubes by adding 2 mL of 10 mM PBS at pH 3.0 and
222 vortexing. The suspensions were maintained at 37 °C with constant end-to-end rotation for a total
223 of 90 min and samples from the supernatant were taken at 0, 5, 10, 15, 30, 60 and 90 min of
224 incubation and replaced with an equal volume of PBS buffer, pH 3.0. After 90 min, pH was
225 raised to 7.0 with 0.1 N NaOH and the suspensions were further incubated at 37 °C with constant
226 end-to-end rotation for a total of 6 h, taking samples from the supernatant as described before, at

227 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, 60, 120, 240 and 360 min of incubation. Determination of OVA concentration in
228 the supernatant was carried out with a Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit.

229 ***In vitro* evaluation of unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogel's**
230 **targeting capabilities**

231 *Cell culture*

232 L929 fibroblasts and RAW 264.7 macrophages cell lines (American Type Culture Collection
233 (ATCC, Rockwell, MD) were cultured in Dubelcco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM)
234 supplemented with 10 % fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% L-glutamine and 1% penicillin and
235 streptomycin³². Cultures were maintained in T-75 flasks (Corning, Corning, NY) at 37°C in
236 humidified environment of 5% CO₂ (Sheldon Signature HEPA Clean CO₂ incubator , VWR).
237 The medium was replaced every other day and the cells were routinely passaged at 80%
238 confluence. For experiments, cells were detached mechanically and adjusted to required
239 concentration of viable cells, by counting in a hemocytometer.

240 *In vitro nanogel cytotoxicity*

241 L929 fibroblasts and RAW 264.7 macrophages cells were seeded at 20,000 cells per well in 96
242 well-plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc Microwell Microplates, Waltham, MA) in phenol red free
243 DMEM with 2% FBS and incubated at 37 °C, 5% CO₂ for 24 hours before testing. Cells were
244 incubated with particle suspensions at concentrations of 1, 0.5, 0.25, and 0.125 mg/mL in phenol
245 red free DMEM with 2% FBS. Lived control wells received only medium, and lysed control
246 wells were included. Following 2 and 48 h incubation, the particles were removed and cells were
247 rinsed 3x with sterile Hank's balanced salt solution (HBSS). Cell viability was then assayed by
248 adding the CellTiter® Aqueous One Solution reagent (MTS, Promega) directly to the culture
249 wells and incubating for 2 h. Finally, the absorbance at 690 nm (background) and 490 nm (MTS
250 assay) was recorded using a microplate reader (Synergy HT, BioTek Instruments, Inc.,

251 Winooski, VT). 690 nm readings from each well were subtracted from absorbance (OD) values
252 at 490 nm, and the viability fraction was defined as:

$$253 \quad \text{Viability fraction} = \frac{OD_{\text{sample}} - OD_{\text{lysed cells}}}{OD_{\text{lived cells}} - OD_{\text{lysed cells}}} \quad (2)$$

254 *Evaluation of uptake by RAW 264.7 macrophages cell line*

255 In order to visualize nanogel uptake by confocal microscopy, unmodified and mannan-modified
256 nanogels were conjugated to the CFTM488A Amine fluorescence dye (Biotium, Hayward, CA).
257 Briefly, 10 mg of nanogels were suspended in 0.1M MES buffer at pH 4.7 (1% w/v) and
258 vortexed. 5 mg of Sulfo-NHS and 5 mg of EDC were added and suspensions were mixed gently
259 by vortexing and incubated for 30 min at RT with constant end-to-end rotation. After initial
260 activation of surface carboxylic acid groups, nanogels were centrifuged at 8,000 rpm for 5 min,
261 the supernatant was removed and nanogels were re-suspended in 500 μ L of 0.1M MES buffer
262 (pH 4.7) by vortexing. This step was repeated one more time to ensure unreacted reagents were
263 removed. After final wash step, nanogels were re-suspended in 500 μ L of 0.1M MES buffer (pH
264 4.7) and 5 μ L of 1 mg/mL CFTM488A Amine fluorescence dye were added. Nanogel suspensions
265 were mixed by vortexing and incubated at RT for 2 h with constant end-to-end rotation. After
266 reaction time was completed, nanogels were washed twice as previously described, once with
267 0.1M MES buffer, pH 4.7 and a second time with DI water. Finally, nanogels were dried under
268 vacuum for at least 2 h.

269 To study nanoparticle interactions with macrophages, RAW 264.7 macrophages cells were
270 seeded in 12-well culture plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc Microwell Microplates, Waltham, MA)
271 containing an acid washed 18 mm circular cover slip on each well (Thermo Fisher Scientific
272 Inc.) at a density of 0.5×10^5 cells/well in supplemented DMEM and incubated overnight at 37
273 $^{\circ}$ C in humidified environment of 5% CO₂. Next day, the medium was removed by aspiration and
274 1 mL of CFTM488A-labeled nanogels suspension in 10 mM sterile calcium and magnesium free

275 PBS were added to the cells to achieve a final concentration of 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Cells were
276 subsequently incubated for 2 h at 37°C in humidified environment of 5% CO_2 . After incubation
277 time, cells were washed 3x with sterile ice cold calcium and magnesium free PBS to remove
278 extracellular and non-adherent particles, and then fixed with 0.3 mL of 4% paraformaldehyde in
279 PBS (pH 7.4) for 10 min at RT. Cultures were washed again 3x with HBSS and stained with 0.2
280 mL of Alexa Fluor®594 wheat germ-agglutinin (WGA) at 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in HBSS for 10 min at RT in
281 complete darkness. Cells were further washed 2x with HBSS and once with DI water, and the
282 coverslips were finally mounted by placing them cells-side down on a drop of Pro-Long with
283 DAPI mounting media (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) on glass slides. The slides were cured
284 overnight at RT and coverslips were stabilized in glass slides by using nail polish. Confocal
285 microscopy was performed using a Leica SP2 AOBS laser scanning confocal microscope (Leica
286 Microsystems, Buffalo Grove, IL). Final image preparation was performed utilizing particle-
287 counting algorithms of ImageJ v1.36b software (NIH, Bethesda, MD).

288 **Cell surface marker expression analysis by flow cytometry**

289 For flow cytometry analysis of surface molecule expression a previous protocol described by
290 Torres, et al was adapted³³. RAW 264.7 macrophages cells were cultured as previously described
291 and seeded in 12-well culture plates at 1×10^6 cells/well in 2 mL of supplemented DMEM
292 media. After overnight incubation at 37 °C in humidified environment of 5% CO_2 , unmodified
293 and mannan-modified OVA-loaded nanogels suspended in culture medium were added to the
294 macrophages cultures at a concentration of 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Unstimulated macrophages and cells
295 stimulated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS, 100 ng/mL) were used as negative and positive
296 controls, respectively. Cultures were incubated for 24 h (37 °C, 5% CO_2). After 24 h of
297 stimulation, macrophages were harvested and washed with azide free and serum/protein free
298 PBS, and then stained for cell viability with the fixable viability dye eFluor® 780 (eBioscience,
299 San Diego, CA) for 30 min at 4 °C. After viability staining was completed, cells were washed

300 with fluorescence-activated cell sorting buffer (FACS, 0.1% w/v sodium azide and 0.1% w/v
301 bovine serum albumin in phosphate buffer saline). 0.1% v/v of unlabeled hamster IgG and 0.1%
302 v/v/ of anti-mouse CD16/CD32 antibody (eBioscience, San Diego, CA) were added to cultures
303 in order to block Fc γ receptors and prevent nonspecific binding. After blocking for 20 min at 4
304 °C, cells were then incubated with the appropriate antibody or isotype control for 30 min at 4 °C.
305 Antibodies used included allophycocyanin (APC) anti-mouse MHC II (I-Ad, clone AMS-32-1),
306 PerCP-eFluor® 710 anti-mouse CD40 (clone 1C10), Fluorescein isothiocyanate (FITC)-
307 conjugated anti-mouse CD80 (B7-1, clone 16-10A1) purchased from eBioscience (San Diego,
308 CA), and (PE)/Cy7 anti-mouse CD86 (clone GL-1) and (PE) anti-mouse CD206 (MMR, clone
309 C068C2) purchased from BioLegend (San Diego, CA). Isotype-specific control antibodies
310 included APC-conjugated mouse IgG2b κ , PerCP-eFluor® 710 rat IgG2a κ , FITC-conjugated
311 Armenian Hamster IgG purchased from eBioscience (San Diego, CA), and (PE)/Cy7 Rat IgG2a
312 κ and (PE) rat IgG2a κ from BioLegend (San Diego, CA). Single color compensation controls
313 were prepared using OneComp eBeads (eBioscience, San Diego, CA) as described by
314 manufacturer. Following staining, cells were washed in FACS buffer and fixed in 3%
315 paraformaldehyde and stored at 4 °C until analysis. Analysis was performed on a BD
316 LSRFortessa cell analyzer (BD Bioscience, San Jose, CA) and data were analyzed using FlowJo
317 software (TreeStar, Inc., Ashland, OR).

318 **Analysis of released cytokines by ELISA**

319 Cell-free supernatants were collected from DCs cultured for 24 h in the presence of unmodified
320 and mannan-modified OVA-loaded nanogels and stored at -20 °C until analysis. Pro-
321 inflammatory cytokines IL-6 and TNF- α were measured using cytokine-specific ELISA kits
322 from eBioscience (San Diego, CA).

323 **Statistical analysis**

324 All the experiments were performed with $n = 3-6$, and data were analyzed with the statistical
325 software IBM SPSS Statistics 20. One-way ANOVA and Student-Newman-Keuls. Post Hoc tests
326 were used to determine statistical significance among treatments, and p -values <0.05 were
327 considered significant.

328 **Results and discussion**

329 **Synthesized P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels showed pH-responsive profile required for oral** 330 **delivery of protein antigens**

331 The surfactant-free emulsion polymerization technique³⁴⁻³⁶ is a useful approach to overcome
332 problems related with the presence of these additives and their purification processes, such as
333 instrument calibration, pore size determination and destabilization of polymer latex by
334 coagulation or flocculation after surfactant removal³⁷. As a consequence of the lower total
335 particle surface area that can be stabilized in absence of surfactant, particle number is
336 characteristically lower in surfactant-free emulsion polymerization processes, resulting in a
337 higher particle size. However, this can be overcome by the addition of a non-ionic stabilizer such
338 as PVA²⁶. Stabilizers provide colloidal stabilization via steric interference with the Van der
339 Waals attraction between polymer particles³⁷. Several researchers reported the size dependence
340 on the concentration of a stabilizer for various polymerization systems³⁸⁻⁴⁰, describing an
341 inversely proportional relationship between size and stabilizer concentration.

342 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that this technique is used to produce pH-
343 responsive nanogels. In these pH-responsive systems, the polymer network contains weak acid
344 or base groups that undergo complexation by hydrogen bonding, thus exhibiting pH dependent
345 swelling properties with fast expansion and contraction⁴¹. In the case of acrylic acid-based
346 copolymers¹⁷, the monomer MAA provides the weak acid groups that allow for swelling
347 performance⁴¹. In the proposed system, MAA is copolymerized with the monomer HEMA,

348 which has many advantageous properties for biomedical use including high water content, low
349 toxicity and tissue compatibility²⁷. The presence of polar groups of hydroxyl and carboxyl and
350 hydrophobic α -methyl groups⁴² allows for the interaction with proteins of different isoelectric
351 points⁴³, and the selection of co-monomers can provide further improvement of HEMA
352 copolymer carrier's performance for a given compound⁴⁴.

353 In this study, different ratios of monomers HEMA:MAA (i.e., 3:1, 1:1 and 1:3) in combination
354 with different concentrations of stabilizer, PVA (i.e., 1, 2 and 3 wt%) were assayed to obtain
355 particles with an adequate pH-responsive behavior and size (i.e., nanosized particles). Aiming to
356 obtain a non-variable mesh size in all the formulations, not leading to significant differences in
357 posterior assays, cross-linker concentration, EGDMA, was used in the constant amount of 1.0
358 mol% of total monomers for all the formulations, which has been a widely assayed cross-linker
359 ratio for HEMA-MAA hydrogels^{45, 46}.

360 *SEM*

361 Freeze-dried particles were mounted on aluminum stubs and observed by SEM. Representative
362 SEM microphotographs of 1:3 HEMA:MAA nanogels are shown **Figure 1**. Spherical particles
363 with size in the nanometer range were observed, which is in agreement with light scattering
364 measurements. Some aggregation was noted in all the samples, which may be due to the
365 dehydration process during freeze-drying of nanogels and sample preparation.

366 *Light scattering*

367 The elucidation of size was crucial in understanding the performance of the P(HEMA-co-MAA)
368 delivery system and its potential behavior throughout human gastrointestinal (G.I.) tract.
369 Monodisperse polyanionic nanoparticles were obtained for all the formulations assayed with size
370 ranging from 292 nm to 1.5 μ m as determined by SEM (**Fig. 1**) and corroborated by light
371 scattering measurements. No significant differences in particle size were observed when PVA

372 concentrations varied from 1 to 3 wt % (data not shown). This is probably due to the fact that the
373 minimum concentration assayed was already enough to provide steric stability to the amount of
374 particles produced and their surface in contact with the continuous phase. Thus, higher stabilizer
375 concentrations did not provide further stability to the suspension, and formulations with 1 wt %
376 were selected to continue with further studies.

377 The pH responsive swelling profile of the particles produced with 1 wt % PVA is pictured as of
378 z-average diameter and zeta potential values in **Figure 2**. As it can be observed, all the
379 formulations showed swelling/deswelling pH-responsive behavior due to hydrogen bonding with
380 a clear transition in size and zeta potential measures between pH values of 5.8 and 7.0. This pH
381 transition frame is attributed to MAA pK_a value, which is 4.6 but has been reported to undergo
382 significant modifications due to the change of chemical environment upon polymerization⁴⁷.
383 Furthermore, a similar increase in pH transition values was previously reported for various
384 copolymer pH-responsive networks containing MAA^{40, 48, 49}. Owing to this transition, the
385 nanogel particles exhibited an increase in zeta potential and a decreased in z-average diameter as
386 pH was decreased in the experiment; at high pH values, pendent MAA groups are ionized,
387 showing zeta potential values of -45 mV and leading to the dissociation of the interpolymer
388 network²⁰. The electrostatic repulsion causes the polymer complex to swell, and hence z-average
389 diameter values of 961.8 nm to 1.5 μ m were observed depending on the polymer composition
390 (**Fig. 2**). These divergences in particle size are probably due to the degree of MAA present in the
391 network; higher contents of ionizable monomer led to higher repulsion and dissociation within
392 the polymer network. Previous studies on MAA copolymerized with N-vinyl pyrrolidone
393 (P(MAA-co-NVP)) reported higher degree of hydrogen bonding complexation at low pH values
394 when higher concentrations of MAA were employed⁴⁹, which accounts for a larger z-average
395 diameter transition in particles with higher contents of MAA. Furthermore, similar results were
396 previously obtained with P(MAA-g-PEG) networks¹⁷, where a higher MAA feed ratio correlated

397 with the more dynamic change in size on gel nanospheres as the pH was increased. Therefore,
398 larger swollen particles were obtained for 1:3 HEMA:MAA nanoparticles relative to 1:1
399 HEMA:MAA particles, which were subsequently larger than 3:1 HEMA:MAA particles. As pH
400 was progressively decreased, hydrogen bonding minimized the electrostatic repulsion leading to
401 deswelling of particles, which reached similar sizes of about 300 nm for all the formulations.
402 These size values are also in accordance with published studies on pH-responsive acrylic-based
403 polymer nanospheres¹⁷. Zeta potential values increased as well to near 0 mV due to surface
404 charge neutralization, which led to poor colloidal stability of the suspension and difficulty for the
405 measure of particles³² at pH values lower than 3 (data not shown).

406 Hence, particle size at the swelled state could be modulated based on the initial monomer feed
407 ratio employed, which is highly advantageous since nanoparticle size plays a critical role in cell
408 uptake⁵, amount of delivered antigen¹ and bias of immune response⁸, as previously exposed. In
409 addition, formulation parameters such as initiator molar ratio and monomers and/or cross-linker
410 concentration in the system could be further explored in terms of particle size modulation. Since
411 the obtained results were optimal for the purpose of this study, and higher swelling potentially
412 leads to higher release of compounds within the delivery system, 1:3 HEMA:MAA particles
413 were selected to continue with further studies.

414 **Mannan-attachment to nanogels surface was accomplished by amine-carboxylic acid** 415 **coupling**

416 Mannan, an intended ligand to CLR on APCs, was attached to nanogels in three steps, which are
417 depicted in **Figure 3A**. In the first step, carboxymethylation of mannan (CM-mannan) was
418 achieved by reaction of mannan with sodium hydroxide and chloroacetic acid. Infrared
419 spectroscopy indicated the presence of carbonyl group at 1740 cm as evidence of
420 carboxymethylation, which was corroborated by an acid-base titration procedure (data not
421 shown). In the second step, CM-mannan was reacted with ethylenediamine hydrochloride in the

422 presence of EDC and Sulfo-NHS as coupling agent to form aminoethylcarbomethylmannan
423 (AECM-mannan). CHN elemental analysis indicated the substitution degree of between 7-9%.

424 In the final step, AECM-mannan was conjugated on the surface of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
425 by an amine-carboxylic acid coupling reaction. Specifically, the amine groups introduced to
426 mannan after the reaction with ethylenediamine were reacted with carboxylic acid residues from
427 MAA. To corroborate the attachment of mannan moieties to the surface of the nanogels, a
428 colorimetric phenol-sulfuric acid assay was employed. Higher absorbance at 490 nm, were
429 observed for mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels when compared with unmodified
430 nanogels (data not shown). By utilizing a standard curve generated with AECM-mannan and
431 unmodified nanogels as controls to account for polymer interference with the assay, the mannan
432 content was found to be about 20 µg per mg of nanogels. Mannan presence, integrity and activity
433 after attachment to P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels was also confirmed by the agglutination test
434 with Con-A, which binds specifically with saccharides such as mannose, fructose, and glucose
435 residues. As shown in **Figure 3B**, the measured absorbance at 550 nm increased when Con-A is
436 added to MN-modified nanogels suspension, while the unmodified formulation show no
437 significant increase in measured absorbance. The results clearly indicate that mannose residues
438 from mannan are capable of interacting with the lectin receptors, which may result in efficient
439 internalization by cells. The increase in absorbance is due to the increase in turbidity caused by
440 agglutination of Con-A on interaction with mannose.

441 **OVA antigen was efficiently loaded into P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels**

442 An OVA loading optimization experiment was performed to determine the appropriate amount
443 of time for loading of OVA into the nanogels²³. From this study, it was concluded that maximum
444 loading efficiency was achieved at the longest incubation time tested, *i.e.* 24 h, with a loading
445 efficiency value of 24 wt. % and 12 wt. % of loaded OVA relative to particle mass. Loading
446 efficiencies were also determined after the collapsing of particles with the addition of HCl and

447 posterior washing of remaining amounts of OVA not encapsulated, as registered in **Table 1**.
448 After the addition of acid, loading efficiency increased to 57%, which is most probably due to
449 the entrapment of the protein within the collapsed polymer network. It should be noted that
450 loading efficiencies are usually reported to decrease after acid addition, due to the collapse of the
451 network forcing some of the protein out of the polymer²³. In comparison, loading efficiency of
452 OVA into the particles proved to increase after HCl addition, which could be attributed to the
453 isoelectric point (IEP) of the protein that determines a net charge at low pH values. Hence, the
454 protein would lose molecular mobility with the decrease of pH, favoring the entrapment within
455 the polymer complex. In addition, the loading efficiency value experimented a slight decrease
456 after washing the particles by centrifugation, which is probably due to certain amounts of OVA
457 adsorbed on particles surface in the collapsing step that were eliminated after washing.

458 **Both MN-modified and unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels release antigen at pH of**
459 **the small intestine**

460 OVA release studies aimed to simulate pH changes that the P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels would
461 experience *in vivo* when passing through the stomach and into the small intestine (*i.e.*, from an
462 acidic pH to a neutral pH). **Figure 4** shows the results of OVA release from P(HEMA-co-MAA)
463 and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) (MN-modified NPs) nanogels. At low pH, both
464 unmodified and MN-modified nanogels limited the release of OVA from the particles. After 90
465 min the release media pH was increased and the protein was rapidly released from the particles,
466 which is in agreement with the previous experiments. P(HEMA-co-MAA) carriers released the
467 maximum amount of protein after 30 min at pH 7.4. MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) carriers
468 also showed a fast initial release but reached 81.65% of total OVA at that time point, showing a
469 lower release rate in a second stage and reaching the maximum amount of protein release at 210
470 min. This slower release profile could be attributed to electrostatic interactions between the
471 released protein and mannan molecules on the particles surface. Similar results were reported in

472 the literature for calcitonin-loaded and insulin-loaded poly(methacrylic acid-grafted-ethylene
473 glycol) (P(MAA-g-EG)^{20, 23}. Another possibility to explain the slower released profile observed
474 from mannan-modified particles could be a restricted swelling potential due to surface
475 crosslinking by the presence of mannan molecules. More detailed characterization is needed to
476 corroborate any of these hypothesis but those studies are out of the scope of the present work.
477 This study demonstrated that OVA is quickly released from both unmodified and mannan-
478 modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) carriers after the pH is increased above the pK_a of MAA.
479 Furthermore, release results indicate that the change in pH between stomach and the small
480 intestine can be used as a physiologic trigger to release OVA from these nanogels. As the
481 particles pass into the small intestine, they would recognize a pH shift to ~7, which ionize MAA
482 pendent groups triggering decomplexation of the hydrogel and quick release of the compound at
483 the targeted site. Although, the fast release profile observed at pH 7.4 for both unmodified and
484 mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels it may translate to premature release of the
485 antigen before nanogels can reached the Payer's patches for M-cell uptake; these nanogels would
486 meet the criteria of antigen protection from degradation upon mucosal delivery⁶, initially stated
487 in this work.

488 ***In vitro* evaluation of unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogel's** 489 **targeting capabilities**

490 *In vitro* biocompatibility of unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels was
491 demonstrated in fibroblast (L929) and macrophages (RAW 264.7) cell cultures

492 Fibroblast (L929) and macrophages (RAW 264.7) cells were used to determine biocompatibility
493 of non-loaded and OVA-loaded, unmodified and MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels.
494 Results are shown in **Figure 5**. Cell viability was determined using MTS assay after 2 and 48 h
495 of incubation with the particles. Both cell lines presented similar responses when exposed to the
496 different carrier formulations, showing no cytotoxic effect of neither of the formulations assayed.

497 Post hoc tests were applied to cell viability data with IBM SPSS Statistics 20 software to analyze
498 if there were statistically significant differences between values. Student-Newman-Keuls test
499 showed no statistically significant differences between the treatments and provided an only
500 statistical subgroup ($p=0.053$).

501 *Both unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels were internalized*
502 *effectively by macrophages but higher internalization rates were observed for MN-modified*
503 *nanogels*

504 To determine the effect of mannan-attachment to the surface of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels in
505 the internalization of nanogels by macrophages, microscopic analyses were performed. As
506 shown in **Figure 6A**, both unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels were
507 efficiently internalized by macrophages. These qualitative findings were corroborated by
508 applying particle-counting algorithms, results of this quantitative analysis are summarize in
509 **Figures 6B** and **6C**. Higher percentage of cells internalizing nanogels (**Figure 6B**) as well as
510 average number of nanogels internalized per cell (**Figure 6C**) resulted when macrophages were
511 incubated with mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels when compared with unmodified
512 nanogels. Together, this data shows that surface functionalization of P(HEMA-co-MAA)
513 nanogels with mannan significantly improved their internalization by macrophages. The
514 enhanced uptake of mannan-modified nanogels increases the likelihood that more macrophages
515 would be available to present antigen to T cells following *in vivo* administration of these
516 particles.

517 These results also suggest that mannan-modified nanogels are internalized by a different
518 mechanism than unmodified nanogels. While mannan-modified nanogels may interact directly
519 with CLRs present on macrophages driving a receptor-mediated endocytosis mechanism^{12, 50}, a
520 non-endocytotic or energy-independent pathway may be involved in the internalization of
521 unmodified nanogels⁵¹. To corroborate this hypothesis, internalization studies were performed at

522 4 °C which inhibits all energy-dependent pathways^{51, 52}. As shown in **Figure 6B**, while
523 incubation the percentage of cells internalizing unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels did not
524 decrease significantly when incubation was performed at 4 °C, the internalization of mannan-
525 modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels was significantly decreased (from ~60% to 25%) at this
526 temperature. These results suggests that endocytotic or energy-dependent mechanisms are
527 involved in the cellular uptake of mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels, although
528 more detailed studies around this observation are needed to establish a clear mechanism for
529 internalization of both unmodified and MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels.

530 *Mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels enhanced the expression of co-stimulatory*
531 *molecules on macrophages*

532 Flow cytometry was utilized to evaluate the stimulating effects of unmodified and mannan-
533 modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels in comparison with LPS, a pathogen associated
534 molecular pattern (PAMP) known to enhance the expression of cell surface markers on APCs by
535 interacting with specific PRRs⁵³. Stimulation of RAW 264.7 macrophages with unmodified or
536 MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels enhanced the expression of the T cell costimulatory
537 molecules CD86 (**Figure 7B**), CD40 (**Figure 7C**), and CD80 (**Figure 7D**) over non-stimulated
538 cells. Moreover, the expression of these cell surface marker molecules was, in most of the cases,
539 comparable or at higher levels than the positive control (i.e., LPS). This is also noted in the
540 histograms by the increased shift from the isotype control (**Figure 7A**). The expression of these
541 costimulatory molecules on APCs is of great relevance since they play an important role in
542 further antigen presentation and activation of T cells, which may lead to the generation of a most
543 robust immune response⁵⁴. The enhanced stimulation of costimulatory molecules by unmodified
544 P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels may be due to the interaction of macrophages with the
545 hydrophobic surface of these nanogels, which may result in endogenous danger signals, which
546 are known to stimulate robust immune responses in the absence of inflammatory response⁵⁵.

547 Consistent with this statement, the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines (i.e., IL-6 and TNF-
548 α) by macrophages was not increased after stimulation with unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA)
549 nanogels when compared with non-stimulated controls (data not shown).

550 As shown in **Figure 7C**, cells incubated with mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
551 showed the higher expression of CD40 surface molecules. The expression of this molecule on
552 APCs has been directly correlated to increase in particle internalization⁵⁶, which is consistent
553 with the results previously discussed in which MN-modified nanogels were internalized at a
554 higher rate than unmodified nanogels (**Figure 6**).

555 Previous published work showed that di-mannose-functionalized polymer nanoparticles enhance
556 the expression of DC activation markers (i.e., MHC II, CD40, and CD86) by targeting the
557 mannose receptor (MMR, CD206)¹⁵. The stimulating effect of mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-
558 MAA) nanogels may, therefore, be attributed to the direct targeting of CLR_s (i.e., MMR) on
559 macrophages with the mannan ligands attached on the surface of nanogels. To corroborate this
560 hypothesis, the expression of the macrophage mannose receptor (i.e., CD206) was assessed after
561 stimulation with MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels. Results did not show an increase
562 in the expression of MMR compared to unmodified nanogels (data not shown). These findings
563 may indicate that the mannan-ligands presence on the surface of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
564 do not interact directly with the mannose receptor on macrophages. However, the observed
565 increase in internalization and enhancement in the expression of co-stimulatory molecules may
566 be attributed to targeting of other CLR_s, such as the DC-SIGN receptor. It has been previously
567 suggested that DC-SIGN recognized and interact more specifically with high-order mannose
568 structures^{12, 14}, which is the case of the mannan-ligand utilized in the design of these novel
569 nanogel carriers.

570 The observed efficiently internalization of both unmodified and mannan-modified nanogels by
571 macrophages and the ability of both carrier formulations to induce the expression of

572 costimulatory molecules indicate the potential of both systems for efficient antigen delivery to
573 APCs. The need of taking an extra bioconjugation step (i.e., mannan functionalization of
574 nanogels) will depend on the specific targeting capabilities that could be obtained with the
575 incorporation of surface ligands and the influence that direct targeting will have in the
576 modulating the induced immune response, which needs to be addressed mainly in in vivo
577 systems.

578 **Conclusions**

579 Oral drug delivery is a route of choice for vaccine administration because of its non-invasive
580 nature. However, most bioactive drugs such as peptides and proteins result in low bioavailability
581 lack of control on absorbed dose and need of adjuvants. An effective oral vaccine delivery
582 system that overcomes these problems must protect the antigen from degradation upon mucosal
583 delivery, penetrate mucosal barriers and control the release of the antigen and costimulatory and
584 immunomodulatory agents to specific immune cells (i.e., APCs). In this paper, mannan-modified
585 pH-responsive P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels were synthesized and their effectiveness as carriers
586 for oral vaccination was assessed. The nanogels showed pH sensitive properties, entrapping and
587 protecting the loaded cargo at low pH values, and triggered protein release after pH switching to
588 intestinal pH values. Unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels showed intrinsic adjuvant
589 properties by being efficiently internalized by macrophages and induced the expression of
590 costimulatory molecules. Surface decoration with mannan as carbohydrate moieties resulted in
591 enhanced internalization by macrophages as well as increasing the expression of relevant
592 costimulatory molecules (i.e., CD40) at higher levels to those observed for unmodified nanogels.
593 Collectively, these findings indicate that both unmodified and mannan functionalized P(HEMA-
594 co-MAA) nanogels are a viable strategy for enhancing antigen delivery to APCs and, in turn,
595 these delivery platforms may facilitate a more efficacious oral vaccination regimen.

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685 **Figures**

687 **Figure 1.** SEM images of freeze-dried spherical polyanionic P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
688 (magnification 3,412 x – 10,156 x, Hitachi S-5500 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)
689 (30kV)).

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692 **Figure 2. Synthesized P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels showed pH-responsive profile required**
 693 **for oral delivery of antigens.** pH-responsive swelling of polyanionic P(HEMA-co-MAA)
 694 nanoparticles prepared with 1:3; 1:1 and 3:1 HEMA:MAA ratio, 1 mol% EGDMA and 1 wt %
 695 PVA. Z-average diameter (filled icons) and zeta potential values (empty icons) were measured
 696 using dynamic light scattering with Malvern ZetaSizer Nano ZS Instrument equipped with MPT-
 697 2 Autotitrator. Formulations were not colloidal stable at low pH values; measures at pH values
 698 lower than 3 are not shown.

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701 **Figure 3. Mannan-attachment to nanogels surface was accomplished by amine-carboxylic**
 702 **acid coupling.** **A.** Molecular structures of mannan and intermediates products, as well as
 703 mannan-attached to nanogels surface. **B.** In vitro ligand agglutination of unmodified and MN-
 704 modified nanogels with Con-A. Optical density was measured at 550 nm. Values represent mean
 705 \pm SD (n=3).

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708 **Figure 4. Both MN-modified and unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels release antigen**
 709 **at pH of the small intestine.** OVA release profiles from pH-responsive P(HEMA-co-MAA) and
 710 MN-P(HEMA-co-MAA) NPs incubated in 10 mM PBS undergoing a shift in pH from 3.0 to 7.4
 711 at 90 min.

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713

714 **Figure 5. In vitro biocompatibility of unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-**
 715 **MAA) nanogels was demonstrated in fibroblast (L929) and macrophages (RAW 264.7) cell**
 716 **cultures. A.** Fibroblasts L929 and **B.** RAW 264.7 cell viability fraction assayed with MTS after
 717 48 h incubation with unmodified and OVA-loaded unmodified, and Ova-loaded MN-modified
 718 P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels. No significant cytotoxicity was observed at the concentrations
 719 tested with either cell line. $n = 3-6 \pm SD$.

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722 **Figure 6. Both unmodified and mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels**
 723 **were internalized effectively by macrophages but higher internalization rates were**
 724 **observed for MN-modified nanogels. A.** Chemical attachment of amine-containing
 725 fluorescent dye CFTM 488A (green) to the surface of P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels
 726 allow for imaging using confocal microscopy. Cell membrane (red) and nucleus (blue)
 727 were stained after 2 hr of incubation of cells with the unmodified or mannan-modified
 728 nanogels. **B.** Percentage of cells internalizing unmodified or mannan-modified
 729 nanogels. **C.** Average number of unmodified or mannan-modified nanogels per cell.
 730 Data are expressed as the mean \pm SEM of three independent experiments. Different
 731 letters indicate statistically significant differences between the groups at $p < 0.05$.

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734 **Figure 7. Mannan-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels enhanced the expression**

735 **of co-stimulatory molecules on macrophages.** Expression of cell surface molecules on

736 the surface of macrophages (RAW 264.7) cells was studied by flow cytometry after

737 incubation of cells with unmodified and MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels for

738 24 h. A. Represented histograms comparing between treatments in red and the isotype

739 non-specific control in grey. Treatments represented in the histograms include

740 unmodified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels, MN-modified P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanogels,

741 and unstimulated cells and Lipopolisaccharide (LPS)-stimulated cells were used as

742 negative and positive controls, respectively. Below the histograms is the complete set of

743 results for mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) expression of RAW 264.7 macrophages

744 cell surface markers: **B.** CD86, **C.** CD40, and **D.** CD80. Data are graphed as mean \pm

745 SEM of a minimum of three replicates per stimulation group. * and # represent groups

746 that are significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from the non-stimulated or LPS treated DCs,

747 respectively.

748

749 **Tables**750 **Table 1.** OVA Loading Efficiencies for P(HEMA-co-MAA) nanoparticles after 24 h incubation

751 and both before and after acid collapsing.

	Loading efficiency (%) ± SD	wt (%) loaded (mg OVA/mg particles) ± SD
Before collapsing	24 ± 9.6	12 ± 4.2
After collapsing	57 ± 3.6	29 ± 0.5
After washing	51 ± 2.0	26 ± 0.6

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